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pinagpalapublishingservices@gmail.com

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LEVEL OF IMPLEMENTATION OF LEARNING ACTION CELL (LAC) IN SAN LUIS DISTRICT

Michelle O. Pagkaliwagan, MAED

Teacher III

Tungal Elementary School

Batangas Province, Batangas, Region IV-A CALABARZO, Philippines

Research Abstract

Learning Action Cell (LAC) as quality learning circle for teacher takes a big part in the lives of teachers as it promotes professional development, with the end goal of improving the teachers' teaching skills and pupils' performance. In relation to this, the study intended to determine the level of implementation of LAC in the elementary schools in San Luis District where the researcher employed the descriptive method of research and self-made questionnaire as the main data gathering instrument. Respondents were 111 elementary school teachers from San Luis District during the school year 2020-2021.

Ranking, percentage, weighted mean, t-test of significance and Pearson coefficient of correlation were applied in the treatment of the analyzed and interpreted data. As revealed in the study, majority of the respondents have been in service from 1 to 9 years. Most of them are females. Respondents were adequately competent in setting targets on desired learners' progress. The implemented learner-centered assessment was performed with adequate competence. There was no significant difference on the assessments of the respondents on the implementation of the learning action cell (LAC) and performance of teachers during LAC sessions when grouped based on their gender and their highest educational attainment. The roles of the respondents in the implementation of the learning action cell and their performance during LAC session have no significant relationship. An enhancement plan or activities was proposed to keep themselves abreast and further enhance teacher's capabilities in conducting LAC sessions. Based on the findings and conclusions of the study, and in order to enhance the implementation of LAC in the District of San Luis, the researcher recommended that school heads and LAC coordinators should have a thorough and careful planning on the implementation of LAC sessions for the success of the activity. There should be regular assessment and reporting of the learners' data of the formative assessment to devise instructions. Close supervision by school heads and master teachers on the implementation of LAC should be conducted regularly. School heads should encourage inclusion and participation of the community in the indigenization process so as culture sensitive be considered. A similar study should be conducted to enhance the level of implementation of LAC sessions.

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